

Paraphrase Strategy in Translating Indonesian Novel into English

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ABSTRACT: This research article discusses one of the translation strategies namely paraphrase. The method used is a mixed method of descriptive-comparative method with both quantitative and qualitative research approaches. The data source is the translation of a novel, *Tarian Bumi* written in Indonesian language as the source language text and 'Earth Dance' in English as the target language text. The data used for this research are taken from the first part of the novel. The background of this research is the phenomenon showing that from all the sentences in the first part of the novel, more than 50% are being paraphrased. To identify what linguistic units are paraphrased, what kinds of paraphrase involved and which paraphrase is used more than others are the objectives of this research. The results show that the paraphrases involve all linguistic units ranging from word, phrase, clause, to sentence. The paraphrase can be used individually or in a combination consisting of two paraphrases and among the four kinds of paraphrase, the explicative paraphrase is used more than others either it is used individually or in combination.

KEYWORDS: explicative paraphrase, linguistic unit, paraphrase strategy, *Tarian Bumi* 'Earth Dance', translating a novel

I. INTRODUCTION

Due to the fact that the story in a novel mostly about the reflection of the real life which will reveal the cultural background of the people in the novel, there are various strategies or techniques of translation can be the options in translating a novel. And this will involve the genre, the writing style of an author, the formality of a language and other detail things. When dealing with the details of the uniqueness of one culture, one style, and one kind of formality of a language, for instance, the work of a translation becomes more challenging than any other texts like journal articles, text books, and others. This means that a translator not only deals with the languages of both texts; the source language text and the target language text in translating a novel, but also with other knowledge like culture, anthropology, translation studies, literature studies, motivation, appreciation, and others [1]. The basic needs a translator needs to improve herself or himself are not only by mastering the grammar of the source and the target language but also by comprehending the culture of the source language as well as the target language.

The object of this research is the first part of a novel, an Indonesian novel entitled *Tarian Bumi*, written by Oka Rusmini. The novel has been published since 2007 and the one that is used for this research is the third edition published in 2017. The novel is translated into English by Rani Amboyo and Thomas M. Hunter into Earth Dance. The first part of the novel is chosen to be the data source as the first part is mostly an introductory part where any necessary information is shared and explained. It is from this first part the next information shared in the following parts are based on.

This research is based on one single background that is the existence of paraphrase strategy found in the data source. It can be observed that almost all sentences in the first part of the novel are paraphrased. This indicates that almost all information in the sentences there needs to be explained, to be clarified with more words and with different word order, with different structure. The phenomenon leads to some research questions of what linguistic units are paraphrased; what kinds of paraphrase found in the target novel and which paraphrase shows the highest frequency of usage among the four. The answers to the research questions show the objectives of this research.

It is expected that the result of this research will give more insights, more options, to translators of Indonesian-English and English-Indonesian as well as to the students of Translation Major and to the researchers of Translation Studies. The result of the research can be used as a guideline in reproducing the source text in the target text. By this information, the students and the researchers will gain the knowledge on how to make the information in the source language text, Indonesian language, more readable, more communicative in English.

The efforts done by a translator can be observed by the translation instruments a translator uses and this depends on the problems he/she deals with. A paraphrase strategy or technique or procedure with its main function to make the text more understandable,

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clearer, more concise by giving explanation, by making implicit information explicit using different choice of words, different syntactic structure [2] becomes one of the solutions in translating a novel.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

References used in this research article are taken from several sources: journal articles, books, internet webs. The references involve 2 things: the use of paraphrase in research articles and the researches on the novel *Tarian Bumi* 'Earth Dance'. What references are taken from the previous researches are as follow:

- (1) Taken from a journal article where paraphrase is used as one of the 20 strategies in translating subtitle in a film; in this strategy proposed by Hariyanto, an Indonesian scholar, in Hastuti (2011), a translator explains a part of a sentence based on his own interpretation [3]; the differences between this article and this present article is in the data source as well as the theory of paraphrase. The data source in this research is a film while in the present research is a novel. Regarding the use of paraphrase, although the research uses paraphrase as a translation strategy the one that is used in the present research is the paraphrase theory from different scholar;
- (2) It is almost the same as in the first reference, paraphrase is used in translating a film as a subtitle. Paraphrase is used as a translation technique as an attempt to express the idea and the message of the source language text be more general and more acceptable in a different language text (the target language text), for example, translating the text which has implicit meanings into explicit [4]. The paraphrase uses in the present article involves not only the shift from implicit meaning into explicit but also others like from no existence into existence as an additional information;
- (3) The next reference involves the use of paraphrase in translating a novel where paraphrase is a strategy to deliver a statement, a phrase, or even one single word using different words (quoted from Danielsson, 2007). What needs to be underlined is that the restatement of idea or message though can be expressed in different words, different figures of speech yet the effect or the meaning in the target language has to be the same [5]. This present article uses paraphrase also as a translation strategy and in translating a novel also, yet the theory about paraphrase is taken from a different scholar, not Danielsson's;
- (4) The next reference deals with paraphrase as an amplification in the analysis of translation strategy used in Indonesian BBC News and this research discusses the effect of this strategy to the translation quality [6]; this present article uses paraphrase itself as the translation strategy not as amplification and no quality of translation is discussed;
- (5) This fifth reference is used as it involves the use of paraphrase as a translation technique also as a part of amplification technique proposed by Molina Albir [7], it can be seen from a journal article discussing the translation of a novel from English into Indonesian. The paraphrase technique involves the adding of detail information that is not formulated in the source language text as well as explicitation, explicative paraphrase, and legitimate and illegitimate, including footnotes [8]; this present article does not make use all those kinds of paraphrase.

As to see the use of the same data source, a novel, *Tarian Bumi* 'Earth Dance', the references taken from previous researches are as follow: (i) this reference as well as the last reference deal with the data source, the novel *Tarian Bumi* 'Earth Dance'. It discusses the translation of the Indonesian conceptual metaphors found in the novel [9]; this present article excludes the translation of metaphor; and (ii) the last previous research taken as a reference is a thesis. It is taken due to the fact that the research uses the same data source. However, the analysis does not include Translation Studies instead it uses a Critical Discourse Analysis talking about stratification system (Case system) in Balinese culture written in the novel [10].

From the references quoted in this research article, it can be located the position of this present research that the paraphrase translation strategy in translating a novel, Indonesian novel, *Tarian Bumi* into English 'Earth Dance' discussed here is an original work. There has not yet been any research found dealing with this topic.

Regarding the term paraphrase in Translation Studies, it can be identified that it is used in various approaches. Paraphrase has been the object of discussion among the experts of Translation Studies whether it is a part of translation techniques [2] or it is a part of translation strategies [11], or even it is as a part of translation procedures which reveals as the amplification procedure [12]. Whatever it is attached to, there are 2 main points about paraphrase that all experts agree with: the form of paraphrase and the main function of paraphrase. The form of paraphrase is a restatement using more words, different words, different word order and why paraphrase is used deals with several reasons: to make implicit information into explicit [4], to give explanation to cultural words [13], and to give explanation or clarification [2].

The term paraphrase used for this present research refers to the paraphrase as a translation strategy taken from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/294087258> Paraphrasing as a translation strategy. It is written by Lucyna Harmon (2013) Rzeszów University. According to Harmon [14], the term paraphrase refers to a translation strategy and it is classified into 4 kinds: (i) simple paraphrase-this involves shifts and modifications where all information mentioned in the source language text can be found in the target language text; (ii) distributive paraphrase-referring to its name, this kind of paraphrase deals with the distribution of information, it is different from what is found in the source language text where it can be observed from the use of

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punctuation or word order and it can be observed also by the use of fused or split sentences; (iii) explicative paraphrase-this involves not only additional information but also the selection of applied words so the result seen in the target language text does not need to be longer although it usually is. What can be underlined is that this kind of paraphrase makes the target language text clearer and more precise; (iv) omissive paraphrase-it deals with the omitting some information so usually the target language text becomes shorter than the source language text although it does not have to be. In this kind of paraphrase some information can be skipped by selection of applied words as well. All four kinds of paraphrase can be found in this research.

III. METHODOLOGY

This research involves a mixed method research of quantitative research as well as qualitative research. Quantitative research deals with number and qualitative research deals with words [15]. It is a quantitative research as it deals with number or quantity: the number of paraphrase found in the text and the occurrence of certain paraphrase in the text compared to others. This research also uses qualitative research as it mainly involves words or qualitative phenomenon, quality or kind: what linguistic units are paraphrased and how it is paraphrased.

The method used in this research is a mixed method of descriptive-comparative method [16]. Descriptive-comparative method is used as this research deals with the act of comparing two texts; source language text and target language text and with the act of describing the analysis as well as the result of the research the way it is. This includes all steps as follow: (1) Reading the source language text, *Tarian Bumi*, a novel; (2) Reading the target language text, *Earth Dance*, its translation in English; (3) Comparing the two texts to find out the similarities and the difference between the two texts regarding the occurrence of paraphrase; (4) identifying the kinds of paraphrases found; (5) identifying the linguistic units which are paraphrased; (6) Counting the quantity of paraphrase found; (7) Counting the quantity of the occurrence of certain paraphrase compared to others; the last step is to describe everything into a research article.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of this research show that from around 205 sentences in the first part of the Indonesian novel, more than 50% of them are paraphrased. The 150 sentences are not fully paraphrased, some are only the clauses, some are only the phrases, and some other are only the words. Based on the statement it can be inferred that the paraphrase occurred in all linguistic units ranging from word, phrase, clause into sentence. The next thing that should be underlined is that the paraphrase covers all 4 kinds of it and most of them do not work individually. They are in combination of at least 2 paraphrases.

This research article is not going to describe the discussion of all 150 paraphrase cases; only some of them that can represent each case occurs in the data. The discussion is divided into 2 parts; the paraphrases used as one single kind and the paraphrases used in combination. The paraphrases discussed are put in a table.

Table 1. Paraphrases Used as One Single Kind

No.	Source Language Text	Target Language Text
1.	" <i>Meme...! Meme...!</i> "	" <i>Meme...! Meme...!</i> " a young girl screamed.
2.	" <i>Luh, Meme sering berkata, kan? Jangan sering berteriak.</i> "	" <i>Luh! How often have I told you not to shout like that?</i> "
3.	Karena dia seorang putri Brahmana,	It's because she's the daughter of a <i>brahmana</i>
4.	Ketika perempuan itu menari seluruh mata seperti melahap tubuhnya.	When she dances, all eyes devour her.

Table 1 consists of 4 data representing the kind of single paraphrase found in the sentence. It covers the 4 kinds of paraphrases. In data (1) the unit linguistic which is paraphrased is a sentence in a form of utterance. The word *Meme* there is a Balinese term for a mother. Those two sentences end with exclamation mark reflecting the intensity of the calling. In the text there, it is not explicitly stated who is calling and how the call is expressed. Using an **explicative paraphrase**, the translators add the data with information on who makes the call; **a young girl** and how she does it: **screamed**. The additional information **a young girl screamed** is an effort done by the translators to make the information from implicit becomes explicit. It is an act of explaining. To be qualified as an explicative paraphrase, it can be seen that the information given in the target language is longer and is more precise. The readers of the target language will get the information on who does the call and how she does the call. There is only one single paraphrase identified in data (1).

In data (2) there are 2 whole parts of sentences being paraphrased. The first sentence "*Luh, Meme sering berkata, kan?*" when translated literally it is 'Luh, Meme often said, didn't I?' is a question tag where the addressee "Luh" is mentioned in the beginning of a sentence then followed by coma indicating that the one put in the beginning of a sentence is not the subject. The subject is *Meme* 'mother' and she reminded Luh by making the statement into tag question. The content of what she would like to remind "Luh" is put in the next sentence: *Jangan sering berteriak* 'Do not scream often'. Using distributive paraphrase, the coma

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after the name Luh is replaced by an exclamation mark and put it as a single sentence “Luh!”; then the content of the first sentence which is in question tag is made into a longer question; it is not in a question tag anymore, beginning with a question word “how often” and the second sentence in the source language text which is a negative command *Jangan sering berteriak* is added together in a longer question: **Luh! How often have I told you not to shout like that?** To be qualified that the two sentences in the source language have been distributive paraphrased in the target language text can be observed from the number of sentences revealed. There are 2 sentences in the source language text: question tag and negative command to be restated into the same number of sentences (2 sentences) but with different types: exclamatory sentence and interrogative sentence; and with different word order.

In data (3) the linguistic unit which is paraphrased is a word, *karena* ‘because’. Using a simple paraphrase, the word *karena* is translated into **it’s because** where the word **because** is preceded by an introductory clause **it’s**. To be qualified that it is a simple paraphrase used in data (3) is the modification (the introductory clause **it’s**) inserted in the beginning of a sentence. The introductory clause is not necessarily required by the system of English language in the context. The translators could just translate it without any modification, without paraphrasing it yet to make it clearer, they do make the simple paraphrase there.

In data (4) the linguistic unit which is paraphrased is a word, *tubuhnya* ‘her body’. Using **omissive paraphrase**, the word *tubuhnya* is translated into **her**, omitting the word **body**. To be qualified that it is omissive paraphrase used in the data is the shorter expression found in the target language and by skipping information, body. It is assumed that the translators do this due to the fact that the meaning of the word body is covered in the word her.

Table 2. Paraphrases in Combination: Explicative and Distributive

No.	Source Language Text	Target Language Text
5.	Dewa-dewa benar-benar pilih kasih! Seorang perempuan berkata sedikit sinis .	The gods are truly choosy who they smile upon, ” said one woman, her tone touched with cynicism.
6.	Tubuh Putu Sarma begitu luar biasa. Aromanya juga.	Putu Sarma had a such beautiful body and an intoxicating scent.

There are 2 data put in table 2 representing the use of paraphrases in combination of explicative and distributive paraphrases. The information written in data (5) consists of 2 sentences: exclamatory sentence ended by exclamation mark; ***Dewa-dewa benar-benar pilih kasih!*** and the next sentence is a statement; *Seorang perempuan berkata sedikit sinis*. Those two sentences are translated using a combination of 2 paraphrases: explicative and distributive. It is explicative due to the fact that the word *kasih* ‘love or care’ is paraphrased into a clause **who they smile upon** and the phrase *sedikit sinis* ‘a bit cynical’ is paraphrased into **her tone touched with cynicism**. The clause **who they smile upon** is used to make the information clearer or more precise while the clause **her tone touched with cynicism** is used to change the information from implicit into explicit that the way the woman said involving the tone of cynicism. The readers of the target language will get the clear information on what the gods are choosy about and how the woman’s words in the act of saying reveals cynicism. While the second paraphrase which is called distributive paraphrase is located as it can be seen from the phenomenon that the two sentences in the source language text are translated into one single sentence. The two sentences are fused into one so it affects the information structure that it is the woman who said that and it is the same woman who had cynical tone in her statement.

In data (6) the linguistic unit which is paraphrased is a word, *tubuh* ‘body’. Using the combination of **explicative paraphrase and distributive paraphrase** the word *tubuh* ‘body’ is put in a different word order; as a part of subject in the source language text *tubuh Putu Sarma* ‘Putu Sarma’s body’ become a part of object in the target language text, **a beautiful body**. The fronting of the name Putu Sarma to be the subject in the target language makes the information on how the body is expressed clearer and the information added on how the scent of Putu Sarma’s makes the sentence more precise. It becomes clearer with the united information revealed in a fused sentence between *Tubuh Putu Sarma begitu luar biasa* ‘Putu Sarma’s body is so amazing’ and *Aromanya juga* ‘His scent is too’ into **Putu Sarma had a such beautiful body and an intoxicating scent**. The distributive paraphrase strengthens the message in the target language that it is the scent of Putu Sarma’s body which is explained.

Table 3. Paraphrases in Combination: Omissive and Explicative

No.	Source Language Text	Target Language Text
7.	Andaikata perempuan itu seorang Sudra , perempuan kebanyakan, aku akan memburunya sampai napasku habis .	If only she were a commoner, I’d chase her until the end!
8.	Padahal perempuan di atas panggung itu telah memberi banyak kemudahan untuk keluargaku.”	She has made life so much easier for my family!”

Table 3 deals with paraphrases in a combination of omissive paraphrase and explicative paraphrase. In data (7) the linguistic units which are paraphrased are (i) a word, ***Sudra***, ‘the name of the lowest caste (social stratification) in Balinese culture’ and (ii) a

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phrase, *napasku habis*, ‘my breath ran out’. Using omissive paraphrase the term *Sudra*, the name of the lowest caste in Balinese culture, is translated into **a commoner** referring to the information given after the term *Sudra* in the source language. Although the basic message can be conveyed in the target language by the omissive paraphrase yet the detail information that it involves the term *Sudra* as the name of a caste in Balinese culture is not revealed. And using explicative paraphrase the phrase *napasku habis* is translated into **the end** referring to the context that it has an act of chasing so it reflects the meaning of a distance, the end, so there is no more chasing. While in the source language, the end of chasing process is reflected by the phenomenon of having no more breath, the last breath. When a person has no more breath, that means it is the end of his life.

In data (8) the linguistic units which are paraphrased are a word, *padahal* ‘whereas/eventhough’ and a phrase *di atas panggung* ‘on the stage’ and another phrase, *telah memberi banyak kemudahan* ‘has given much easiness’. Using omissive paraphrase, the word *padahal* showing contradiction is omitted as well as the phrase *di atas panggung* reflecting her profession as a dancer. It is assumed that the translators omit the two linguistic units due to the fact that the information has already been discussed in the previous context. Based on that, the readers are not going to lose any information. The omissive paraphrase is used just to avoid repetition there. While the phrase *telah memberi banyak kemudahan* is paraphrased into **has made life so much easier** using explicative paraphrase where the noun easiness is restated by a comparative adjective **easier** to show the intensity of easiness given by the woman; and the word **life** is used to reflect that the easiness given by the woman is not only in some part but the overall part. Although there is an omission in the target language text regarding a certain detail, the basic message of the source language text is similarly conveyed in the target language by revealing the intensity of kindness the woman has done.

Table 4. Paraphrases in Combination: Distributive and Explicative

No.	Source Language Text	Target Language Text
9.	Sari pasti akan girang lalu berteriak sepuasnya menceritakan pada seluruh misan-misannya bahwa dia adalah anak perempuan baik-baik. Keturunan orang terhormat.	No doubt she would scream with delight and announce to the whole world that she was a good girl after all, born from a fine, respectable family.

There is only one data representing a combination of distributive paraphrase and explicative paraphrase put in table 4. The linguistic units which are paraphrased are a word, *pasti* ‘definitely’ and the phrase *girang lalu berteriak sepuasnya* ‘happy then scream unlimitedly’ and *seluruh misan-misannya* ‘all her cousins’ as well as the whole sentence *Keturunan orang terhormat* ‘Born from a respectable family’. Using distributive paraphrase, the word *pasti* which is put after the subject Sari in the source language text is translated into **no doubt** then it is redistributed in the target language to the beginning of a sentence placing before the subject Sari. Not only that, the first sentence of data (9) *Sari pasti akan girang lalu berteriak sepuasnya menceritakan pada seluruh misan-misannya bahwa dia adalah anak perempuan baik-baik* is then combined together with the second sentence *Keturunan orang terhormat* into one single sentence in the target language: **No doubt she would scream with delight and announce to the whole world that she was a good girl after all, born from a fine, respectable family.** There are two cases of distributive paraphrase in data (9). The first distributive paraphrase changes the word order from after subject into before subject which indicates there is a new distribution of information that affects the information structure and the same thing happens in the second distributive paraphrase where the two sentences of data (9) are made into fused sentences. While the explicative paraphrase is used in translating *girang lalu berteriak sepuasnya* into **scream with delight** where the act of screaming is done with delight; it is not two processes happy then scream but it is reflected that the screaming is caused by the happy feeling. By this paraphrase the information in the target language is clearer and more precise on how the girl feels and how the feeling is expressed. The second case of the explicative paraphrase is found in translating a phrase *seluruh misan-misannya* ‘all of her cousins’ into **the whole world**. It is assumed that the translators would like the readers of the target language get more general information instead of the detail one. The whole world is aimed at the world of the little girl where she lives together with all her cousins.

Table 5. Paraphrases in Combination: Omissive and Distributive

No.	Source Language Text	Target Language Text
10.	Kenapa hanya perempuan bangsawan yang diberi seluruh kecantikan bumi!	Why is it that noblewomen are granted all the beauty of this earth?

The last table, table 5 consists of one data reflecting a combination of 2 paraphrases omissive paraphrase and distributive paraphrase. The linguistic unit which is paraphrased is a word, *hanya* ‘only’. Using the omissive paraphrase the word *hanya* is omitted, it is then replaced by the word **that**, a conjunction to emphasize that those who are granted all the beauty of the earth are noblewomen not anybody else. The paraphrase can still convey the same message. In the meantime, distributive paraphrase is used to restate a statement ended by exclamation mark into a question mark. The actual information contained in the sentence of the source language text is not a question; it is a statement expressing a complaint although it is preceded by a question word

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kenapa 'why'. It is restated into a question in the target language not because it needs an answer but more to an act of questioning; an act of complaining as reflected in the source language.

CONCLUSIONS

From all discussion regarding the research questions, it can be concluded that

- (1) The linguistic units which are paraphrased ranging from word into sentence. The highest number of linguistic unit which is paraphrased is word.
- (2) The translation of the novel *Tarian Bumi* involves all 4 kinds of paraphrases. Around 70% of data are translated using a combination of paraphrases and the rest 30% of data are translated using a single paraphrase.
- (3) The highest frequency of paraphrase used in the data is explicative paraphrase either it is used individually or it is used in combination. While lowest frequency of paraphrase used is omissive paraphrase.

This research is not totally completed in a sense that there are still more data which are not studied yet. There are more theories can be applied like translation shifts; syntactic or semantic. As one of the settings in the novel is caste system in Balinese culture, the language of people representing a certain caste can also be studied.

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